

Nature's Remedy : The Role of Herbal Medicine in Modern Dentistry

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Received on: 23 February 2025; Accepted on: 26 February 2025; Published on : 19 April 2025

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Introduction

Medicinal plants have been utilized for centuries in both medical and dental fields and remain widely employed across the globe. Their anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and antioxidant properties, coupled with their biocompatibility, contribute to the increasing interest in herbal medicine.²

Globally, over 90% of school-aged children and many adults suffer from dental caries, highlighting the necessity for improved diagnostic and treatment methods, particularly for pediatric patients³. Meanwhile, the misuse and overuse of antibiotics continue to rise, raising concerns about resistance and safety. Research on dental irrigants reveals limitations and side effects of synthetic agents. For instance, chlorhexidine (CHX) is known to cause tooth discoloration, an unpleasant burning sensation, and temporary loss of taste⁴. Sodium hypochlorite is associated with allergic reactions and tissue toxicity, while calcium hydroxide is ineffective at completely eliminating bacteria from dental tubules².

Additionally, access to synthetic medications is not universal, particularly in developing regions, prompting many to turn to herbal alternatives. In the United States, a 2007 study revealed that 12% of children used alternative medicine, with 5% specifically using plant-based treatments⁵. Given the diverse composition and effects of different plants, this review focuses on various medicinal plants commonly used in dentistry, particularly paediatric dentistry. It aims to explore their advantages and potential side effects, promoting the safe and effective use of herbal medicines in treating oral health conditions in children.

Materials and Method

A Literature Review were performed using the Medline, PubMed and Google Scholar databases and books published in

english with the following search keywords “medicinal plant”, “herb”, “phytotherapy”, “dentistry” and “pediatric”.

Overview of Plant-Based Applications in Dentistry

Plants have played a pivotal role in various aspects of dentistry, contributing to treatments and materials across multiple specialties. For instance:

- **Periodontics:** Aloe vera (medicinal aloe) helps reduce gingival bleeding and inflammation, while *Azadirachta indica* (neem) decreases plaque accumulation. *Pistacia atlantica* (mastic tree) exhibits antimicrobial properties against gingival microorganisms, and *Salvadora persica* (miswak) promotes improved gingival health^{6,7}.
- **Endodontics:** *Morinda citrifolia* (Indian mulberry)⁸, and propolis are employed as irrigants. Propolis is also useful for pulp capping⁹, while *Arctium lappa* (greater burdock)¹⁰ and *Curcuma longa* (turmeric) serve as intracanal medicaments. Turmeric, in particular, aids in endodontic retreatment by dissolving and softening gutta-percha¹¹.
- **Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery:** Products like Ankaferd Blood Stopper®, derived from *Glycyrrhiza glabra* (licorice), *Vitis vinifera* (grapevine), *Alpinia officinarum* (lesser galangal), *Thymus vulgaris* (thyme), and *Urtica dioica* (nettle), are used to manage bleeding. Similarly, aloe vera-based SaliCept patches help reduce the incidence of alveolar osteitis¹².
- **Management of Oral Lesions:** Various medicinal plants are studied for treating

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How to cite this article : Mohit et al. - Nature's Remedy : The Role of Herbal Medicine in Modern Dentistry, AJOCD-HT 2025

oral conditions. *Melissa officinalis* (lemon balm) and *Mentha piperita* (peppermint) are effective against herpetic lesions, with the latter showing strong virucidal activity against HSV-1 and HSV-2²³⁻²⁴. *Candida albicans* infections can be treated with *Coriandrum sativum* (coriander)²⁵, while *aloe vera* and *Portulaca oleracea* (purslane) are beneficial for managing lichen planus²⁶.

Phytotherapy in Pediatric Dentistry

The use of medicinal plants in pediatric dentistry has gained popularity, driven by the perception that they are gentler alternatives to invasive procedures and synthetic medications, with fewer adverse effects. This growing preference has encouraged the exploration of various plant-based properties for treating children.

Preventing Dental Caries

The prevalence of dental caries, combined with the expense of treatment, underscores the importance of preventive measures. Antibacterial agents and fluoride-based products play a crucial role in this effort. Research indicates that certain plants, through their secondary metabolites, can enhance microbial sensitivity. Additionally, they can prevent dental caries by suppressing bacterial growth and acid production, inhibiting bacterial adhesion to tooth surfaces, and blocking the synthesis of exopolysaccharides. For example, some of these plants are mentioned below:

Allium sativum (Garlic) Garlic is known to boost the immune system, lower blood pressure, and reduce cholesterol production in the liver. It is commonly used to manage conditions such as asthma, arthritis, atherosclerosis, and various circulatory and digestive issues. Forms such as fresh garlic oil, raw cloves, and odourless extracts are utilized.²⁰ Research attributes its antibacterial properties to allicin, a key compound in garlic. It has been shown to inhibit the growth of *Streptococcus mutans*, reduce acid production, and stimulate saliva secretion, making it beneficial in the prevention and management of dental caries²⁹.

Azadirachta indica (Neem) Neem has been found to reduce the occurrence of early dental caries and can reverse its progression, showing effectiveness comparable to chlorhexidine by lowering *Streptococcus mutans* levels²¹. It possesses antibacterial properties and acts as a biocompatible antioxidant. Studies reveal that it inhibits the growth of *Streptococcus mutans*, *Streptococcus mitis*, *Streptococcus sanguinis*, and *Streptococcus salivarius*³².

Curcuma longa commonly known as turmeric, possesses antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimutagenic properties. Its use as a mouthwash has been shown to provide quick pain relief. Applying turmeric directly to an aching tooth can alleviate discomfort, while a paste made with turmeric, mustard, and salt is beneficial for managing gingivitis and periodontitis³³. Turmeric also exhibits potent antibacterial activity against *Streptococcus mutans* biofilm, demonstrating efficacy comparable to chlorhexidine (CHX). This makes it a promising agent for preventing dental caries.

Mentha piperita, commonly known as peppermint, has historically been used to treat conditions affecting the stomach, intestines, and muscles, as well as to enhance blood circulation. Today,

it is also employed to address ailments such as colic, fever, nausea, and diarrhea. Its chemical constituents include menthol and methyl acetate. In dentistry, peppermint is used topically to alleviate dental pain and as a mouthwash to reduce gum inflammation³³. Another study found that peppermint oil exhibited local virucidal effects against herpes simplex viruses (HSV-1 and HSV-2)²⁴.

Pistacia atlantica, a member of the *Pistacia* genus, has various parts, such as its resin, leaves, fruit, and aerial components, utilized for medicinal purposes. In Iran, the resin, known as Saqqez, is commonly used as a mouth freshener, antiseptic, and gum tissue fortifier. It is also available as chewing gum to address gastrointestinal issues and motion sickness³⁵.

Storage Media for Avulsed Teeth

When a tooth is avulsed, it is crucial to store it in an appropriate medium to preserve its viability until replantation at a dental office. Common storage media include milk, saliva, and Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS)³⁸.

Camellia sinensis (Green Tea Extract)

- Green tea extract has proven to be as effective as Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) in preserving the viability of periodontal ligament (PDL) cells⁴⁰.

Cocos nucifera (Coconut)

- Research indicates that skimmed and whole milk, natural coconut water, and HBSS are effective in maintaining the viability of PDL fibroblasts⁴¹.

Morus rubra (Red Mulberry)

- Studies show that red mulberry juice at concentrations of 2.5% and 4% outperforms HBSS in preserving PDL cells for 3, 6, and 12 hours. A 4% concentration has been found equally effective as HBSS for up to 24 hours, making it a suitable storage medium⁴².

Salvia officinalis (Garden Sage)

- Contains alpha and beta-thujone, camphor, cineole, rosmarinic acid, tannins, and flavonoids. Commonly used in modern European herbal medicine for treating sore throat and gum inflammation. Its antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral properties make sage extract effective as a storage medium, particularly at a 2.5% concentration, for maintaining PDL viability⁴³.

Propolis

- In vitro studies on dogs demonstrate that propolis is as effective as milk for preserving PDL cell viability. It has been shown to maintain avulsed teeth for up to 6 hours as an appropriate storage medium⁴⁶.

Camellia Sinensis (Green Tea Extract)

Morus rubra (Red Mulberry)

Salvia officinalis (Garden Sage)

Commiphora Myrrha

Curcuma longa

Pistacia atlantica

Endodontic Treatment in Primary Teeth

Maintaining primary teeth during the primary and mixed dentition stages is crucial for ensuring proper space maintenance. Additionally, preserving the health of primary teeth supports the development of permanent teeth⁴⁷. When other options are not viable, endodontic treatment serves as the final approach to retaining primary teeth. Various materials such as zinc oxide eugenol, iodoform-based pastes, and calcium hydroxide are commonly used for endodontic procedures in primary teeth⁴⁹. Medicaments such as formocresol, calcium hydroxide, glutaraldehyde, enriched collagen solution, ferric sulfate, and mineral trioxide aggregate are employed in pulpotomy⁵¹. In another study, propolis and mineral trioxide aggregate were found to be more biocompatible than formocresol and ferric sulfate⁵². For vital pulpotomy in primary molars, formocresol and Ankaferd Blood Stopper® have demonstrated success as pulp-dressing agents in follow-ups extending up to 12 months⁵³. Furthermore, it has been observed that *Allium sativum* (garlic) oil exhibits stronger effects compared to formocresol on the infected pulp of primary non-vital molars⁵⁴. Nonetheless, further research is required to solidify these findings.

Mouthwashes are an effective and convenient way to enhance oral hygiene. Plant-based compounds such as *Salvia officinalis* (sage), *Mentha piperita* (peppermint), menthol, *Matricaria chamomilla* (chamomile), *Commiphora myrrha* (myrrh), *Carum carvi* (caraway seed), *Syzygium aromaticum* (clove), and *Echinacea purpurea* (purple coneflower)⁵⁶ can be utilized in oral rinses to help lower the gingival index⁵⁵.

Adverse Effects

The side effects and toxicity of medicinal plants can be discussed both generally and specifically for each plant. These factors depend on elements such as their chemical composition, potential contaminants, and adulterants. Additionally, certain plants may exhibit synergistic effects when used together. Another critical consideration is the concentration of active compounds within a plant, which can fluctuate depending on the plant part used, the timing of harvest, and environmental factors such as soil and weather conditions. This variability makes the dosage of active compounds inconsistent and unpredictable, particularly in children. Children are especially sensitive due to their smaller body size and reduced detoxification capabilities. Their absorption, digestion, metabolism, and excretion processes differ from those of adults, and their developing liver impacts their ability to detoxify substances. Therefore, it is essential to carefully evaluate the potential side effects and toxicity of medicinal plants before using them in children⁵⁹.

Conclusion

The growing reliance on medicinal plants can be attributed to the side effects and limitations of synthetic drugs, as well as the affordability, accessibility, and biocompatibility of plant-based remedies. However, further research is needed to identify appropriate medicinal plants, their applications, and optimal dosages, particularly for children, to better understand their potential toxicity and side effects.

Acknowledgment

None.

Conflict of Interest

None.

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